

RESEARCH ON TOURISM ACTIVATION PATH OF INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE TOURISM: A CASE STUDY OF XIAOGUO CLAY SCULPTURE IN LINYI, SHANDONG

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Abstract. *As a provincial-level item of intangible cultural heritage, Xiaoguo clay sculpture in Linyi, Shandong carries rich regional cultural connotations and distinctive artistic value, and constitutes a valuable cultural resource in the Yimeng area. Through literature analysis, field investigation, and typical interviews, this paper identifies the difficulties and problems in the activation and utilization of this intangible cultural heritage—Xiaoguo clay sculpture in Linyi—and proposes the following tourism activation pathways. First, emphasis should be placed on the cultivation, nurturing, and motivation of inheritors. By reshaping the value of inheritance, conducting skills training, and establishing an economic incentive mechanism, efforts should be made to attract young people to participate and increase the income of inheritors. Second, promote the integrated innovation of craftsmanship and the diversified development of products. By combining modern aesthetics and practical needs, design themed, serialized, and highly experiential cultural and creative tourism products and tourism projects. Third, integrate marketing. Utilize both online and offline channels to tell the story of Xiaoguo clay sculpture effectively and enhance brand influence.*

Keywords: *Xiaoguo clay sculpture; intangible cultural heritage tourism; tourism activation.*

Аннотация. *В качестве провинциального объекта нематериального культурного наследия керамические скульптуры Xiaoguo в Линии, Шаньдунский провинция, несут богатое региональное культурное содержание и уникальную художественную ценность, являясь драгоценным культурным ресурсом в районе Имон. С помощью анализа литературы, полевых исследований и типичных интервью данная статья выявляет трудности и проблемы, возникающие в процессе активизации и использования этого нематериального культурного наследия - керамических скульптур Xiaoguo в Линии, и предлагает следующие пути активизации в сфере туризма. Во - первых, уделяется особое внимание воспитанию, развитию и стимулированию наследников. Созданием новой ценности наследования, проведением профессиональных тренировок и установлением экономических стимулирующих механизмов, предпринимаются усилия по привлечению молодежи к участию и увеличению доходов наследников. Во - вторых, способствует интеграции и инновациям в ремесле и диверсифицированному развитию продуктов. С учетом современных эстетических и практических потребностей разрабатываются тематические, серийные и ярко экскурсионные культурно - креативные продукты и туристические проекты. В - третьих, проводится интегрированное маркетинговое продвижение. С использованием онлайн - и оффлайн - каналов рассказывается о керамических скульптурах Xiaoguo, что способствует повышению влияния бренда.*

Ключевые слова: *Керамические скульптуры Xiaoguo; Туризм на основе нематериального культурного наследия; Активация в сфере туризма.*

Мақола мақсади. Шандунг вилояти Линий қаласиндаги Шаого килифтойрамалари Провинция савиятидаги материал - диқ бўлган маълумотлар каттаси бўлган, буюқ регионал маълумотлар мавдуи ва ўзига хос саноат қиўтати ўлғирлади, бу Имон ҳудудидаги қимматли маълумотлар қорыги ҳисобланади. Ушбу мақолада адабиётлар тадқиқоти, қуйидаги яратишлар ва типик суҳбатлашувлар орқали, бу материал - диқ бўлган маълумотлар - Линий қаласиндаги Шаого килифтойрамаларини қуйидаги яратиш ва истифода қилиш учун ишораланиш ва муаммоларини кўриб чиқамиз ва қуйидаги туризм қуйидаги яратиш жолларини таклиф этимиз: 1. Вирасатхона ўқитиш, қўпқўрмоқ ва ҳодимлашувга қизиқ бўлиб, уларнинг ўз ҳақида қизиқ ўқитиб, қўл қучаларини оқитмоқ ва иқтисодий ҳодимлашув механизминини янгилаш, ўшбу ишга яшларни тартибга олиш ва вирасатхоналарнинг кишидаги қошишларини қамтариш; 2. Саноатларни *birlashtirish* ва инновацияларни қатқизиб, товарларни кээфойатли янгилаш, ўзгартирган зиҳният ва амалда ишга тизимлаш қизиқлари билан ҳамкорлик қилмоқ, мавзу - оид, тактиланган, қўпжаҳонликдаги туризм қизиқлари ва туризм мақсатларини таъмирлаш; 3. Маркетингни қатқизиб, онлайн ва оффлайн каналларни истифода қилмоқ, Шаого килифтойрамалари ҳақида одамларга алоқа қилмоқ ва бреннинг ҳиссиётини қамтариш.

Асул so'zla: Шаого килифтойрамалари; Материал - диқ бўлган маълумотлар туризими; Туризм қуйидаги яратиш

Intangible cultural heritage, hereinafter referred to as ICH, is an important component of China's fine traditional culture. It carries the historical memory, cultural genes, and spiritual connotations of the nation, and forms an essential foundation of cultural confidence. In the new era, in which the integration of culture and tourism has become a national strategy and both the cultural industry and the tourism industry are developing rapidly, how to effectively activate the contemporary value of ICH resources, realize their creative transformation and innovative development, and enable them to be protected through transmission and renewed through utilization has become an important research topic and practical direction.

Xiaoguo clay sculpture in Linyi, Shandong is rooted in the Yimeng region, has a long history and a distinctive style, and was included in the first batch of provincial-level intangible cultural heritage items in Shandong Province in 2006. Its forms are simple, vivid, and full of vitality, its colors are bright and lively, and its themes are largely derived from local folk life and myths and legends. It possesses high artistic and aesthetic value and also serves as a vivid carrier of local culture, folk beliefs, and regional spirit in Linyi and even the broader southern Shandong region. As a folk art transmitted in living form, Xiaoguo clay sculpture contains rich cultural information and historical memory. It is a valuable cultural symbol of Linyi and an important cultural tourism resource. In recent years, with the growing national emphasis on the protection and transmission of ICH and the deepening integration of the culture and tourism industries, incorporating Xiaoguo clay sculpture into the tourism development system and exploring its pathways for tourism activation are of substantial practical significance for its own sustainable transmission, for enhancing the attractiveness and competitiveness of Linyi's cultural tourism, and for promoting local economic development and cultural prosperity.

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction to Xiaoguo Clay Sculpture

As a distinctive form of folk art in the Linyi area of Shandong Province, Xiaoguo clay sculpture can be traced back to the Xianfeng period of the Qing dynasty. After more than one hundred years of transmission and development, it has become an important representative of

intangible cultural heritage in southern Shandong. This traditional handicraft uses locally distinctive red clay as its main raw material and is carefully produced through twelve traditional procedures, including clay selection, clay screening, shaping, shade drying, firing, and coloring.

In December 2006, Xiaoguo clay sculpture was included in the first batch of provincial-level intangible cultural heritage representative items in Shandong Province, marking official recognition of its cultural value. In terms of artistic expression, Xiaoguo clay sculpture has developed a distinctive style characterized by bold freehand modeling and intense painted coloration. Its themes are rich and diverse, mainly including opera figures, auspicious birds and animals, and folk scenes. Among them, classic images such as the “clay tiger” and the “prosperity chicken” are particularly well known. These clay sculpture works are not merely traditional children’s toys; they are also deeply embedded in the daily life and festival customs of local residents and are closely connected with folk activities in southern Shandong. For example, customs such as displaying clay sculptures during the Spring Festival to pray for blessings and giving clay children at weddings to pray for offspring all reflect the important position of Xiaoguo clay sculpture in the agrarian culture of the Yimeng region. See Figure 1-1 and Figure 1-2.

Figure 1-1 Clay Tiger

Figure 1-2 Opera Figure

1.2 Current Status of tourism activation

1.2.1. Foundations of tourism activation

As one of the first provincial-level intangible cultural heritage items in Shandong Province, Xiaoguo clay sculpture presents the characteristic of having profound cultural foundations but limited industrialization in its tourism product development, which takes place between traditional transmission and the integration of culture and tourism. Relying on its accumulated traditional techniques, Xiaoguo clay sculpture has formed a product system centered on the clay tiger, also known as the clay whistling tiger, supplemented by traditional works such as clay dolls, zodiac figures, and Three Kingdoms characters. These constitute the basic product supply for tourism activation. Market circulation mainly depends on traditional offline channels, such as temple fairs and markets during traditional festivals including the Spring Festival and Mid-Autumn Festival. In addition, as a local cultural gift characteristic of Linyi City and Lanling County, it has generated stable demand in scenarios such as government-enterprise business exchanges and diplomatic gift-giving.

The tourism products of Xiaoguo clay sculpture can be divided into three categories: low-end popular souvenirs, such as zodiac ornaments, priced at 20–50 yuan; high-end customized collectibles, such as replicas of Qing dynasty statues, priced at 500–2,000 yuan, which account for less than 5 percent because of their complex procedures, including hand-painting with mineral pigments and gift-box packaging; and interactive tourism experience products, such as painted DIY experiences, priced at 50–100 yuan per session.

Table 1-1 Summary of the Characteristics of Xiaoguo Clay Sculpture Tourism Products

Dimension	Sub-indicator	Data / Description of Characteristics
Thematic composition	Share of traditional classic themes	>70% (opera mythology / auspicious animal figures)
	Share of innovative contemporary themes	<10% (including anti-pandemic and red-themed works)
Price system	Popular souvenirs	20–50 yuan (zodiac ornaments, clay whistle toys)
	Interactive experience products	50–100 yuan per session (painted DIY workshops)
	Collector-grade handicrafts	500–2,000 yuan (customized replicas of Qing dynasty statues)
Core craft features	Signature technique	Sound-producing “whistle installation” design, such as reed-whistle roosters
	Aesthetic principle of coloring	“Thirty percent shaping and seventy percent coloring,” with ink lines used to “bring out the spirit”
Modeling features		Exaggerated proportions of “resemblance through non-resemblance,” such as the head and body being of equal height

Data source: Xiaoguo Clay Sculpture Product Pricing Archives, Lanling County Intangible Cultural Heritage Protection Center.

1.2.2 New Trends in tourism activation

Against the background of the rise of cultural tourism, especially ICH tourism, the tourism activation of Xiaoguo clay sculpture has shown new trends toward younger and more diversified development. In terms of clay sculpture product innovation, seventh-generation inheritors have led the development of lightweight cultural and creative products such as refrigerator magnets, keychains, night lights, desktop ornaments, and cultural and creative hanging paintings, which accurately meet young consumers’ needs for daily use and tourism commemoration. At the same time, they have explored integrated innovation between clay sculpture and ceramic techniques, thereby improving product durability and appearance. They have also launched mid- to high-end products suitable for home decoration and light-luxury gift scenarios, enriching the product hierarchy of tourism activation. In terms of experiential activation, Xiaoguo Village has relied on ICH workshops to develop educational experience projects, offering half-day to one-day clay sculpture DIY experience services. Owing to its distinctive ICH features, it has become a popular choice for local primary and secondary school

study trips and parent-child tourism, further expanding new scenarios for the tourism activation of Xiaoguo clay sculpture.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Research on Intangible Cultural Heritage

The literature review shows that current international research on ICH mainly approaches the subject from a technological perspective. Massimiliano Pieraccini, from the perspective of the philosophy of technology, systematically deconstructs the driving mechanisms of cultural heritage digitization and the dilemmas of technological ethics, and establishes a three-dimensional analytical framework that includes the motivations for technology adoption, implementation barriers, and solutions [1]. Maria Elena Bonfigli innovatively developed a web-based application that enables the intelligent aggregation of user communities [2]. The craft simulation system developed by Marcello Carrozzino and his team uses three-dimensional modeling and virtual reality technology to visualize the full process of traditional casting techniques, and realizes the immersive dissemination of craft knowledge through multimodal interaction design [3].

The research system of Chinese scholars on intangible cultural heritage can be divided into three core fields. The first focuses on the construction of mechanisms for living transmission. Scholars mostly use case analysis to examine the application value of digital technology in the continuation of techniques. Among them, Chen Shuaiming conducted field research and data collection on the protection and transmission of Jun porcelain firing techniques, analyzed the current situation, and explored new approaches suitable for the digital transmission of Jun porcelain firing techniques [4]. The second focuses on digital archiving and communication pathways, with an emphasis on digital archiving and communication pathways. Zhao Yanyue used information space theory to establish an evaluation model and revealed the positive correlation between the communication effectiveness of Heilongjiang ICH and the degree of resource structuring [5]. The third emphasizes the exploration of innovative transformation pathways. Yu Riji constructed a cultural heritage activation model using augmented reality technology and verified the effect of digital media in expanding the experiential dimensions of ICH [6]. Tan Yiling developed an intelligent recognition system for Dong brocade patterns and established a modern translation mechanism for traditional crafts through machine learning algorithms [7].

2.2. Research on the tourism activation of Intangible Cultural Heritage

Research on the tourism activation of intangible cultural heritage mainly focuses on three major fields. The first is the evaluation of resources for the tourism activation of intangible cultural heritage. Current scholarship has mainly formed a dual-track research approach combining quantitative and qualitative methods. Under the quantitative analytical paradigm, researchers systematically measure the development potential of cultural resources by constructing multidimensional evaluation models. Yin Huaguang's team innovatively proposed a three-dimensional evaluation framework that takes the intrinsic value intensity of heritage, market transformation efficiency, and product development maturity as core indicators [8]. Ouyang Zhengyu employed a combined Delphi-analytic hierarchy process model to establish a progressive evaluation logic of “attractiveness → continuity → carrying capacity,” revealing the value-order pattern of resource development [9]. The second field is research on the pathways for the tourism activation of intangible cultural heritage. Research on pathways for the living transmission of ICH, as a core issue in the dynamic transformation of cultural resources, presents diversified characteristics in the construction of its methodological system. Based on differences

in practical fields, scholarship has formed three basic paradigms: an evidence-based pathway centered on static preservation, a constructive pathway emphasizing the restoration of cultural contexts, and a practical pathway focusing on performance and interaction ^[10]. The evolution of research indicates that the current academic focus has shifted from singular preservation to cross-boundary integrated innovation, forming a compound development model of “heritage plus.” These explorations are, in essence, practice-oriented research paradigms that construct systematic innovation pathways for the adaptive transmission of traditional cultural genes.

The third field is research on mechanisms for the tourism activation of intangible cultural heritage. Academic discussions of the innovative transformation mechanisms of ICH display the characteristics of multidimensional theoretical construction. In the field of cultural brand regeneration, Wang Xiuhong’s team, based on cognitive schema theory, proposed a dual-track mechanism for the regeneration of cultural brand assets: reconstructing the value of traditional elements by decoding historical symbols, or recombining cultural genes through modern design thinking, thereby constructing a model that combines the continuation and innovation of brand memory ^[11]. Zhang Mu, from the perspective of cultural geography, constructed a “three-dimensional driving” theoretical model: the creation of authentic scenarios strengthens cultural identity, the reproduction mechanism activates heritage value, and the co-creation system realizes value transmission among subjects ^[12]. Lin Yan and others, using the theory of the sociology of technology, proposed a “dual-helix” development framework: in the protection dimension, digital archives and ecological monitoring systems are established; in the innovation dimension, technological empowerment and scenario-based reconstruction are promoted, thereby realizing an overall transformation from material production to cultural ecology ^[13]. Research shows that contemporary studies of the living transmission of ICH have moved beyond a single preservation mindset and have formed a multi-level transformation system centered on value innovation.

3. Research Methods

Xiaoguo clay sculpture in Linyi, Shandong is a highly representative traditional folk clay sculpture technique in southern Shandong. It carries the memory of Yimeng local culture and the folk aesthetic tradition. To systematically explore the difficulties and practical pathways of its tourism activation as intangible cultural heritage, this paper collects policy documents from the Linyi Municipal Government and the Linyi Municipal Bureau of Culture and Tourism, as well as operational materials from the Lanling Xiaoguo Clay Sculpture Transmission Base and ICH workshops (<https://wgxj.linyi.gov.cn>), and conducts textual analysis. It adopts a mixed research method that combines field investigation, in-depth interviews, and text mining, integrates quantitative data and qualitative materials, and systematically analyzes the current characteristics, transmission difficulties, and innovative activation pathways of Xiaoguo clay sculpture tourism.

The research team conducted a three-day field investigation in Xiaoguo Village, Xiangcheng Town, Lanling County, Linyi City, in March 2025. The team visited the Xiaoguo clay sculpture transmission institute, ICH workshops, and rural tourism experience sites, and recorded the entire clay sculpture production process, the exhibition design of culture-tourism integration, and tourist experience scenarios. It also tracked and observed tourists’ participation behavior and consumption conversion characteristics. Eighteen key participants were selected for semi-structured interviews. The core groups included government and industry managers, four people, including staff members responsible for ICH protection and rural tourism in the culture and tourism bureaus of Linyi City and Lanling County, with a focus on ICH support policies,

culture-tourism coordination mechanisms, and industrial guidance measures; ICH inheritors, six people, including sixth-generation inheritor Liu Jiangang, seventh-generation inheritor Liu Xia, other core technique holders, and workshop managers, with discussions centered on the current state of technique transmission, difficulties in creative innovation, and pain points in market transformation; tourism operators and cultural and creative practitioners, four people, including heads of rural tourism cooperatives and ICH cultural and creative development enterprises, with analysis of product design, channel operation, and brand-building practices; and tourists and consumer groups, four people, including study-tour groups, folk culture enthusiasts, cultural and creative consumers, and short-video UGC creators, with the aim of identifying their participation motivations, experience perceptions, and factors influencing consumption decisions.

4. Pathways for the tourism activation of Xiaoguo Clay Sculpture

Based on field investigation and in-depth interviews, combined with data mining, this paper identifies three main problems in the activation and utilization of Xiaoguo clay sculpture tourism. First, the aging of inheritors is severe. The average age of existing inheritors is over 50, and the only current provincial-level inheritor has passed away, while there are very few young successors. According to the investigation, there is currently only one provincial-level inheritor, because fifth-generation inheritor Liu Fuxiang had just passed away when the author conducted the field investigation, and one municipal-level inheritor. There are fewer than five young practitioners. The number of traditional production households has fallen sharply from more than 200 at its peak to fewer than 20, and the survival of this ancient technique is facing unprecedented challenges. Second, tourism products are seriously homogenized. Taking tourism commodities as an example, Xiaoguo clay sculpture products on the market are mostly traditional ornaments such as clay tigers and clay dolls, and many of them are produced through mold-based manufacturing. Their shapes, colors, and themes are almost identical. The Xiaoguo clay sculpture products and experience activities in Linyi scenic areas differ very little from clay sculpture handicrafts in other regions in terms of appearance and function, showing serious homogenization. Third, brand marketing is weak. The channels for publicizing and promoting Xiaoguo clay sculpture as ICH are relatively limited and mainly rely on traditional offline exhibitions and scenic-area displays. New publicity channels such as new media and online platforms are insufficiently used. On short-video platforms, social media, and other communication platforms with large traffic flows, there is relatively little content related to Xiaoguo clay sculpture. Its communication scope remains limited, making it difficult to reach broader potential tourist groups.

According to the difficulties in the tourism activation of Xiaoguo clay sculpture, the following activation pathways are proposed.

4.1. Solving the Inheritor Dilemma and Consolidating the Foundation of Transmission

In response to the prominent aging of inheritors, the shortage of young successors, and the sharp decline in production households, the core task is to construct a three-in-one transmission system of “transmission + cultivation + incentives” and to break through the difficulties of technique transmission.

In terms of transmission, the cultural value of Xiaoguo clay sculpture should be reshaped. Through media publicity, cultural festivals, and other activities, the folk cultural and artistic value behind it should be explored, social recognition of ICH and awareness of protection should be awakened, and a social atmosphere conducive to the transmission of the technique should be created.

In terms of cultivation, relying on the ICH support policies of the culture and tourism departments of Linyi City and Lanling County, a special transmission fund for Xiaoguo clay sculpture should be established, with a focus on supporting municipal-level inheritors in conducting technique instruction and filling the transmission gap left by the death of the provincial-level inheritor. Local primary and secondary schools and vocational colleges should be jointly engaged to establish elective courses and practical training bases for clay sculpture techniques. Inheritors should be invited to enter campuses to carry out hands-on teaching, cultivate young people’s interest in traditional clay sculpture techniques, and identify potential inheritors among student groups. At the same time, technical enthusiasts should be recruited from society, free skills training should be provided, and a reserve talent pool for inheritors should be established.

In terms of incentives, a sustainable economic incentive mechanism should be established. An initial fund should be created through government subsidies and ICH special funds, income generation through tourism activation should be developed, and cash subsidies, honorary recognition, and other forms of support should be given to inheritors who persist in transmission and actively innovate. This would enable inheritors to obtain tangible economic returns and enhance the willingness of young people to enter the field.

4.2. Solving the Homogenization Problem and Enhancing Competitiveness

Product homogenization is a key bottleneck restricting the tourism activation of Xiaoguo clay sculpture. Efforts should therefore be made in three dimensions: work innovation, craft upgrading, and scenario adaptation, in order to create tourism products with clear brand recognizability.

In terms of work innovation, inheritors should be encouraged to create on the basis of traditional forms while integrating Yimeng cultural elements and contemporary topics. For example, regional themes such as red culture and rural folk customs may be incorporated to design differentiated clay sculpture forms. Second, a research team composed of folklorists, artists, and ICH inheritors should be established to create works based on folk stories, festival customs, daily-life scenes, and current social topics in southern Shandong, Shandong Province, and China more broadly. For example, by combining the local Spring Festival custom of “sending tigers to pray for blessings,” a zodiac-themed clay sculpture gift box can be designed, with a story booklet included in the box to explain the folk cultural meaning of the tiger image in warding off evil and bringing blessings.

Innovation in craft integration should be deepened. On the basis of the existing combination of clay sculpture and ceramics, cross-boundary integration with fabric, wood, and other materials should be attempted to enrich product categories and textures. Furthermore, differentiated product tiers should be developed according to differences in tourism consumption scenarios. Affordable lightweight cultural and creative products should be launched for general tourists; customized light-luxury gifts should be created for high-end consumer groups; and simple DIY material kits should be designed for study-tour groups, thereby achieving precise matching between products and demand.

4.3. Strengthening Marketing and Expanding Influence

In response to the problems of single brand publicity channels and limited communication scope, the traditional marketing model should be broken through, and a comprehensive brand communication system integrating offline and online channels should be constructed.

At the offline level, in addition to relying on existing ICH exhibitions and scenic-area displays, linkage with core local tourism routes in Linyi should be strengthened. Characteristic display and experience zones should be established at key sites such as Lanling National Agricultural Park and Yimeng red tourism scenic areas. Clay sculpture performances, DIY experiences, and other activities should be carried out in combination with folk festivals to improve on-site tourist attraction. At the same time, cooperation with culture and tourism departments and travel agencies in surrounding cities should be strengthened to promote the integration of Xiaoguo clay sculpture into the regional tourism product system. At the online level, the advantages of new media communication should be fully used. A professional operations team should be formed to publish content on platforms such as Douyin, Xiaohongshu, and WeChat Channels, including the clay sculpture production process, inheritor stories, and product introductions. Through short videos, livestreaming sales, influencer cooperation, and other methods, brand exposure should be expanded. Official online sales channels should be established, scattered e-commerce stores should be integrated, and a unified brand flagship store should be created to achieve the integration of “publicity + sales,” break geographical limitations, reach broader potential tourist groups, and enhance the brand awareness and influence of Xiaoguo clay sculpture.

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